

Of 165 new rice varieties released to farmers in Asia over a 5-year period, 64% either were progeny of IRRI rices or were IRRI varieties or experimental lines. Twenty-two percent of the rices were developed at IRRI and 42% were progeny of local crosses involving an IRRI parent. One hundred and sixty-five newest varieties released from 1970 to 1975 at 29 agricultural experiment stations and universities in 10 Asian nations, 1975.

Forty-two percent of the varieties were progeny of crosses involving an IRRI variety or line as a parent. (Of the 129 locally developed varieties, 54% were IRRI progeny.) A total of 64% of the sample of 165 newest varieties in 10 countries were either progeny of IRRI rices or had been developed at IRRI. ❧

Advanced breeding lines in 10 Asian nations

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Because most of the future rice varieties released for farmer use in Asia will come from advanced yield trials, IRRI collected information on the types of plant materials included in the trials. Rice breeders were surveyed at 28 research centers in 10 countries in mid-1975. The research project was partially funded by a research grant from The Rockefeller Foundation.

It was found that 4,163 advanced breeding lines were being tested in 29 yield trials at the 28 stations. The mean number was 144 lines/trial, with a range of from 12 to 630 lines/trial.

For most of the trials, the responsible breeder indicated how many of the advanced lines were developed at that

Data were collected on 4,021 breeding lines of rice in 27 advanced yield trials in Asia. *a*. Fifty-nine percent of the advanced lines originated from crosses made at the local research centers; 41% originated from crosses made outside of the local centers. *b*. Of 1,406 introduced lines in 17 trials, 60% came from other research centers in the same country and 39%, from IRRI. From a survey of advanced experimental lines of rice in 9 Asian nations, 1975.

station and how many came from outside sources (other breeding centers in that country, other countries, or IRRI). These data were collected on 4,021 breeding lines in 27 advanced yield trials in 9 countries.

Fifty-nine percent of the genetic material (2363 lines) originated from local crosses made at the breeders' stations; 41% (1658 lines) originated outside of the stations (see figure, *a*).

Next, the origin was determined of the introduced lines (the advanced lines that did not come from local crosses). Data were obtained for 1,406 of the introduced breeding lines in 17 advanced yield trials in 8 countries.

Sixty percent of the introduced genetic material (842 lines) came from crosses made at other research centers within the same country as the surveyed experiment station; 39% (543 lines) came from IRRI; and about 1% (21 lines) came from breeding programs in other Asian nations (see figure, *b*).

To further measure the diversity of the genetic background of improved local lines, breeders at 20 research centers in 8 countries were asked to indicate the number of crosses from which they selected 3,791 locally developed lines in 22 advanced trials. The lines had been selected from 443 crosses – an average of 8.6 advanced lines/cross. ❧

Effect of seedling on the growth and yield of rice varieties

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Rice varieties Bala, Saket 1, and Ratna were transplanted at 24, 29, 34, 44, and 49 days to study the growth behavior and extent of yield reduction when transplanting is delayed. The experiment was conducted at Allahabad Agricultural

Institute during the 1976 kharif season using a split-plot design with four replications. Varieties were in main plots and seedlings of different ages were in subplots.

When older seedlings of the short-duration variety Bala were transplanted, tiller number and yield were consistently reduced. Saket 1 and Ratna (medium- and long-duration rices) gave higher values when planted at 29 days of age than when planted at any other age (see table). The short-duration variety may be transplanted until the age of 34 days,